
ROLE OF THE LAW ENFORCING AGENCIES IN CURBING WHITE COLLAR CRIMINALITY: A CASE STUDY OF THE NATIONAL ACCOUNTABILITY BUREAU OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

White-collar crime is classified as commercial fraud, customer deception, slander, insider trading on the stock market, corruption, and other types of dishonest business strategies. White-collar crimes are regularly renewed to deceive the general public and the government, resulting in billions of rupees in losses. Fake account frauds, large-scale governmental corruption, Ponzi schemes, and theft of government funds all continue to claim victims today. Corruption and swindling have existed in this realm since the beginning of existence. White-collar crime has a long and illustrious history in our society. As a society, we are unable to learn from our mistakes and continue to fall prey to a variety of fraudsters. Unfortunately, Pakistan inherited this malady at its creation, and it kept on spreading with time. This research paper seeks to establish an understanding of white-collar crimes/scams dealt with by the law enforcement agencies like FIA, ANF, Police, FBR, and the highest anti-corruption organization, the National Anti-Corruption Bureau (NAB), which has been assigned to deal with white-collar crimes such as Tax evasion scandal, Pakistan Steel Mills scam, fake accounts, anti-money laundering cases, and their legal enforcement in Pakistan. The findings revealed that there are misuse of the offices and positions. Most often, those in positions of authority are the ones who commit schemes and fraud. It is also evident that institutional mechanisms are regularly used by people in positions of power to hurt and persecute opponents. It is concluded that white-collar crimes are serious but they differ and each case should be treated differently.

Keywords: White-collar crimes, Accountability, Corruption, Anti-corruption.

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